

The System, Water-Potassium Nitrate-Calcium Nitrate.

BY MOHAMMED ABDUL HAMID AND RAM DAS.

The investigation of the system, water-potassium nitrate-calcium nitrate, formed part of a larger work which was contemplated in connection with the refining of crude saltpetre (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1916, 45, 315T). This system has been worked out at 30° by Barbaudy (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1923, 42, 638-42). The isotherm of the system at 25° is shown in the accompanying figure and the data for this system at this temperature are given in the table.

For the determination of solubility, various complexes were vigorously stirred up to equilibrium in sealed tubes immersed in thermostats kept constant at 25° ($\pm 1^\circ$). The potassium ion was determined by the cobaltinitrite method (Hamid, *Analyst*, 1926, 51, 450) and calcium was precipitated as oxalate and weighed as oxide. The nitrate was determined by a modified method of Schlösing.

Table I.
Composition in g. per cent. Solid phases.

Solution.		Wet residue.		Solid phases.
KNO ₃	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	KNO ₃	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	
27.36	0	—	—	KNO ₃ .
24.85	2.12	59.94	1.45	"
23.83	4.96	64.09	2.17	"
22.19	7.87	—	—	"
21.59	11.49	61.21	5.82	"
20.70	17.34	58.56	8.49	"
20.32	19.14	—	—	"
19.46	31.95	70.01	12.05	"
19.22	40.34	70.20	15.12	"
19.06	49.16	25.97	50.93	KNO ₃ + Ca(NO ₃) ₂ , 4H ₂ O.
10.72	53.26	3.09	65.05	Ca(NO ₃) ₂ , 4H ₂ O.
7.37	54.82	1.00	67.92	"
2.64	56.86	—	—	"
0	57.98	—	—	"

Fig. 1.

It has been observed that, with decreasing potassium nitrate concentration, the solution acquires a marked tendency to remain supersaturated for a considerable time. When an aqueous solution of calcium nitrate, saturated at the boiling temperature of water, is transferred to the thermostat in order to cool it to 25°, it first spontaneously deposits crystals, probably of the anhydrous salt or any of the lower hydrates, which redissolve on further cooling. The solution remains very viscous and crystallisation does not start for a long time. This difficulty was overcome by inoculating the solution cooled to 25° with a crystal of the tetrahydrate. At higher concentrations of potassium nitrate no such difficulty was experienced and the solution behaved in a perfectly normal way.

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